

Synthesis and Rearrangement of some α -Substituted-phenyl- α,α' -dialkoxy Ketones

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The rearrangement of 1,3-dimethoxyalkan-2-ones to give methylglyoxal dimethyl acetals represents a novel rearrangement reaction, in which 1,3-sigmatropic migration of methoxyl group may be involved¹. The experimental results show that rearrangement of α -substituted-phenyl- α,α' -dialkoxy ketones (**2**) catalysed by *p*-toluene sulphonic acid in methanol give substituted benzylglyoxal dialkyl acetals which have been identified by their *p*-nitrophenylosazones (**3**).

Results and Discussion

α -Substituted-phenyl- α,α' -dialkoxy ketones (**2**) were synthesised from α -substituted-phenyl- α -alkoylalkanoic acid (**1**) in three steps. **1** was converted to acid chlorides by thionyl chloride, the acid chlorides reacted with diazomethane to form α -substituted-phenyl- α -alkoxy- α' -diazoketones and the diazoketones were alcoholysed to yield α -substituted-phenyl- α,α' -dialkoxy ketones (**2**). Compound **2** could be distilled under reduced pressure and a component of lower boiling point was proved to be substituted benzaldehyde dialkyl acetal. Before distillation, it is necessary to withdraw an aliquot of the crude product and heat it to over 200° to ensure that there is no unreacted explosive diazoketones left in the crude product. The unreacted diazoketones could be converted to alkoxy ketones by adding more alcohol to the crude product and stirring the mixture at 40° for 30 min. The distilled products are usually quite pure through a 15-cm Vigreux column. Higher purity could be obtained by liquid chromatography

on silica gel eluted with diethyl ether-light petroleum ether. The title compounds (**2**) are colourless or pale yellow liquid, which are difficult to be crystallised but form thick liquid. Nmr spectra of **2** show that the two hydrogens of CH₂ are a little different (~ 0.05 ppm) in chemical shift probably because of the asymmetry of the carbonyl plane.

Rearrangement of α -substituted-phenyl- α,α' -dialkoxy ketones (**2**) gave substituted benzylglyoxal dialkyl acetals which were easily converted to *p*-nitrophenylosazones (**3**) in methanol by addition of the reaction mixture to a solution of *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine after completion of the rearrangement. The rearrangement reaction took place preferably in protonic solvent catalysed by acid. The rearrangement rate was quite low in absence of acid and almost no rearrangement was observed in hydrocarbon solvent such as hexane. Protonic solvents and trace of acid may accelerate formation of enol of **2**, which is necessary for the rearrangement.

1 **2** **3**

- a, R = Me, R¹ = H, R² = *p*-MeO-C₆H₄
b; R = Me, R¹ = H, R² = *p*-MeO-*m*-Cl-C₆H₃
c; R = Me, R¹ = Me, R² = C₆H₅
d; R = Et, R¹ = H, R² = C₆H₅

Experimental

α -Substituted-phenyl- α -alkoxyacetic acid (**1a**, **1b**,

1d) were prepared from substituted benzaldehydes² and purified by recrystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether. α -Phenyl- α -methoxypropanoic acid (**1c**) was prepared from methyl phenyl ketone³. Thionyl chloride was freshly distilled before use. Diazomethane was prepared from *N*-nitroso-*N*-methylurea⁴. Nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Varian FT-80A (80 MHz) spectrometer with tetramethylsilane as internal standard and mass spectra on a ZAB-HS (VG) instrument. Melting points are uncorrected.

α -Substituted-phenyl- α,α' -dialkoxy ketones (2).

General procedure : A mixture of α -substituted phenyl- α -alkoxy-alkanoic acid (**1**; 60 mmol) and freshly distilled thionyl chloride (20 ml) was kept at 40° for 4 h. Excess thionyl chloride was then removed by evaporation under reduced pressure. The residual acid chloride was then taken up in anhydrous diethyl ether (100 ml). To the ether solution of acid chloride ca. 0.3 *M* diazomethane solution in ether (300 ml) was added slowly with constant stirring and the temperature was kept between -2 and 0° and the mixture was stirred further for 20 min. Then the mixture was left at room temperature for 1 h. The ether was then evaporated at 25° and the residual diazoketone was dissolved in anhydrous alcohol (200 ml) containing boron trifluoride-diethyl ether (1 ml). It was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. The solvent was then removed at 40° under reduced pressure. The residue was extracted with diethyl ether-benzene (1 : 1 v/v; 80 ml), washed with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and with water and the organic layer was dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. After the solvent was removed, an aliquot of the crude product was subjected to heating over 200° in order to be sure that no explosive diazo compound was remained in the product. The product was distilled under reduced pressure and purified by chromatography on silica gel eluted with diethyl

ether-light petroleum ether (1 : 2, v/v): **2a** (26%), b.p. 104–05°; *m/z* 224 (*M*⁺); δ 7.34–6.83 (4H), 4.78 (1H), 4.20 (2H), 3.79 (3H), 3.33 (3H), 3.31 (3H); **b** (32%), b.p. 110–11°; *m/z* 258 (*M*⁺); δ 7.36–7.13 (3H), 4.76 (1H), 4.19 (2H), 3.86 (3H), 3.36 (3H), 3.34 (3H); **c** (41%), b.p. 82–83°; *m/z* 208 (*M*⁺); δ 7.36 (5H), 4.38, 4.33 (2H), 3.28 (6H), 1.69 (3H); **d** (61%), b.p. 95–96°; *m/z* 222 (*M*⁺); δ 7.36 (5H), 4.39 (1H), 4.29 (4H), 3.56–3.39 (4H), 1.34–1.09 (6H).

Rearrangement of α -substituted-phenyl- α,α' -dialkoxy ketones (2). *General procedure* : Compound **2** (0.70 mmol) was dissolved in methanol (20 ml) containing *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (0.1 mmol). The reaction mixture was warmed at 55° for 50 h, then added dropwise to 0.06 *M* *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine (20 ml) in acetic acid-water (1 : 1, v/v) at 80°. It was warmed for 20 min to complete the reaction. The separated osazone (**3**) was filtrated off and recrystallised from DMF-EtOH : **3a** (52%), m.p. 289–90° (Found : C, 58.69; H, 4.49; N, 18.58. Calcd. for : C, 58.92; H, 4.50; N, 18.75%), *m/z* 444 (*M*⁺-4); **b** (56%), m.p. 268–69° (Found : C, 54.62; H, 3.91; N, 17.20. Calcd. for : C, 54.72; H, 3.97; N, 17.41%); *m/z* 478 (*M*⁺); **c** (58%), m.p. 278–79° (Found : C, 61.02; H, 4.64; N, 19.23. Calcd. for : C, 61.10; H, 4.66; N, 19.44%); *m/z* 428 (*M*⁺); **d** (43%), m.p. 275–76° (Found : C, 59.96; H, 4.30; N, 19.76. Calcd. for : C, 60.28; H, 4.34; N, 20.09%); *m/z* 418 (*M*⁺).

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